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WI-FI,GI-FI,LI-FI

Praveena. P , Pavithra R, & Nandhini . D

IIMSC(SS)

Sri Krishna College Of Arts And Science, Kuniyamuthur, CBE, India

Abstract:

Today various new technologies helps the people more convenient to do the work. In that WI-FI,GI-FI,LI-FI plays the major role among people in sharing of datas, folders etc. This paper deals about the wireless technologies. WI-FI,GI-FI,LI-FI are the wireless communications. They all are the cheap deployment of LAN. These wireless connections can be connected to a network resource such as the Internet via wireless network access point . They all can provides service in to private homes, businesses, as well as in public spaces at Wi-Fi hotspots set up either of free-of-charge or commercially, often using a captive portal webpage for the access. Organizations and several businesses such as airports, hotels, and restaurants provides a free-use hotspots to attract customers .They all offers a faster information and provide them in a les time and at less cost.Gi-Fi provides the high security and les consumption of time.

Key words: LAN, WI- FI, wireless network, hotspots

INDRODUCTION:

WI-FI is a local area wireless technologies which provides an electronic devices to exchange data or connect to internet using radio waves.

Many devices like personal computers, video games, camera, tablets, digital audio players can have WIFI.

WI-FI can connect to the network such as internet through the wireless network access point or a hotspot which range from 20

meters indoor and greater range in outdoors. Using this we can provide sending information wirelessly to another devices which are connected through the local network .

Wi-Fi may be the less secure than wired connections because an intruder does not need any physical connections. Wi-Fi brand included Wireless Local Area Network(WLAN) connections, device to device connectivity(data cables), Personal Area Networks(PAN),Local Area Networks (LAN) and even some limited Wide Area Networks(WAN) connections. To connect to the Wi-Fi LAN, a computer must be with a wireless network interface controller. This combination of computer and interface controller is called a *station*. All the stations shares a single radio frequency communication channel. Transmissions on the channels are received by all the stations within a range. A carrier waves are used to transmit the data in packets, called Ethernet frames". Each station is constantly tuned in into the radio frequency communication channel to pick up the available transmissions.

WI-FI INTERNET ACCESS:

A Wi-Fi-enabled device can be connect to the Internet within the range of a wireless network . The coverage of one or more (interconnected) access points called hotspots that can be extended from an area as small as a few rooms to as large as many square kilometers. Wi-Fi provides services in private homes, businesses, and also in public spaces at Wi-Fi hotspots set up either free-of-charge or commercially, using a captive portal webpage for access. Many organizations and businesses, such as airports, hotels, and restaurants, often provide free-use hotspots to attract customers. Routers which incorporates a digital subscriber line modems or a cable modem and a Wi-Fi access point, set up in homes and other buildings, will provide Internet access and internetworking to all devices connected to them, wirelessly or via cable.

CITY-WIDE WIFI:

Many cities around the world is constructed by city-wide Wi-Fi networks. In 2004, Mysore city became India's first Wi-Fi-enabled city. A company called WiFiNet has set up hotspots in the city Mysore, covering the complete city and a few nearby villages. Many traditional college campuses in the world provides at least partial wireless Wi-Fi Internet coverage known a campus wide WI-FI.

ADVANTAGES:

Wi-Fi allows cheaper deployment of local area networks (LANs)and also provides spaces where cables cannot be run, such as outdoor areas and historical buildings, can host wireless LANs. Manufacturers are building wireless network adapters into most laptops and their price of chipsets for Wi-Fi continues to drop, making it an economical networking option included in even more devices. Wi-Fi is more suitable for latency-sensitive applications (such as voice and video) and Power saving mechanisms which extends battery life.

SAFETY:

The World Health Organization (WHO) says "there is no risk from low level, long-term exposure to Wi-Fi networks" and the United Kingdom's Health Protection Agency reports that exposure to Wi-Fi for a year results in the "same amount of radiation from a 20-minute mobile phone call". A review of studies involving 725 people that claimed electromagnetic hypersensitivity found no evidence for their claims.

LI-FI:

Li-Fi or **light fidelity**, refers to 5G visible light communication systems using light from light-emitting diodes(LEDs) as a medium to deliver networked, mobile, high-speed communication in a similar manner as Wi-Fi. Li-Fi can be used to off-load data from existing Wi-Fi networks to provide capacity for the greater downlink demand as complementary to the existing wireless or wired network infrastructure.

Li-Fi could lead to the Internet of Things, which is everything electronic which are connected to the internet, with the LED lights on the electronics being used as

internet access points. The Li-Fi market is projected to have a compound annual growth rate of 82% from 2013 to 2018 Visible light communications (VLC) signals work by switching bulbs on and off within nanoseconds, which is too quickly to be noticed by the

human eye. Although Li-Fi bulbs would have to be kept on to transmit data, the bulbs could be dimmed due to the point that they were not visible to humans and yet still functional. The light waves cannot penetrate the walls around the bulb which makes a much shorter range, though more secure from hacking, relative to Wi-Fi. Direct line of sight is not necessary for the Li-Fi to transmit signal and the light reflected off of the walls can achieve 70 Mbps.

LiFi are used to extend wireless networks throughout the home, workplace, and in all commercial areas. It is restricted by line of sight. It will be very much simpler if every light in the house simply acts as a wireless network bridge.

PRINCIPLE:

The principle of li-fi is very simple that we have to just switch on the light and switch off the light rapidly so that this light is not visible to the human eyes but a photodetector can pick up the signals send back from the networked devices and a powerline adaptor on board to maintain a connection over electrical wiring back to the router. This technique is called Visible Light Communications - or VLC.

ADVANTAGES:

LI-FI has an advantages that it can be used in electromagnetic sensitive areas like hospitals, aircraft cabins and nuclear power plants. The LiFi can turn any LED lamp into a network connection. LiFi, can work with high frequencies (hundreds of terahertz).

DISADVANTAGES:

The disadvantage is that when suddenly the current is cut off or blocked the connections is disabled.

GI-FI:

GI-FI is a gigabyte wireless integrated wireless transceiver chip which contains small antennas that acts as both transmitter and the receiver which is fabricated using complementary metal oxide semiconductors (CMOS). Using GI-FI we can send a large size files, videos and folders within a fraction of second.

The core component of the GI-FI system is the subscriber station that is available to several accessible parts. It supports several millimeter waves wireless pan networks which is used for communication of the computer devices including the telephones and personal digital assistants.

WORKING OF GI-FI:

Time division duplex is used for both transmitter and the receiver. The data files are converted from IF range to RF range by using two mixers.

ADVANTAGES:

The GI-FI has several advantages like high speed data transfer, low power consumption, high security, cost effective and small size. The Gi-Fi standard has been developed with many objectives in mind.

High speed of data transfer

The main invention of Gi-Fi is to provide higher bit rate .As the name itself indicates data transfer rate is in Giga bits per second. Speed of Gi-Fi is 5 Gbps, which is 10 times greater than the present data transfer. Because of this high speed data transfer, we can swap large video, audio, data files within seconds. Because of wider availability of continuous 7 GHz spectrum results in high data rates.

Low Power Consumption :

It has the large amount of information transfer it utilizes milli-watts of power only. The combined effects of O2 absorption and narrow beam spread results in high security and low interference.

Small size:

The chip is just 5mm per side and has a tiny 1mm antenna and uses the 60GHz 'millimeter-wave' spectrum.

CONCLUSION:

The above all the wireless communications have certain advantages of their own which helps us in several ways .These wireless communications provides transfer of the datas in high speed and they are faster than the Bluetooth.WI-FI,GI-FI,LI-FI are more comfortable and easier to use .This is one of the most important inventions in technology. . Within the five years of time, we will expect that Gi-Fi to be the dominant technology for wireless networking. By that time it will be fully mobile, as well as providing low-cost, high broadband access, with very high speed ,large files can be swapped within seconds which will develop wireless home and office off culture. If the success of Wi-Fi and the imminent wide usage of Wi-Max is any indication, Gi-Fi potentially can bring wireless broadband to the enterprise in an entirely new way.

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